

1 **A network of nuclear receptors expressed in triple negative breast cancer.**

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5 Triple negative breast cancer is defined by lack of expression of hormone receptors *ESR* and *PGR*, as
6 well as the EGFR/ERBB family member *HER2*. The estrogen receptor and estrogen play important roles
7 in transformation in HR+ breast cancers driven by or supported by hormone ligand of a nuclear receptor.
8 By definition, this influence is lacking in the developmental biology of TNBC, suggesting the existence of
9 (an) alternative nuclear factor(s) in TNBC etiology. We conducted discovery of nuclear factors important
10 for transformation in TNBC using whole transcriptome technologies, measuring total transcription in bulk
tumors from humans with TNBC and single tumor cells laser-capture isolated from the primary tumors of
11 humans with TNBC. We identified High mobility group (*Hmg*) family homeobox transcription factors,
12 nuclear machinery that associated with the chromatin (e.g., *ATAD2*), a member of the thyroid hormone
13 pathway receptor that has multiple discrete functions known as *TRIP13*, a nuclear receptor known as
14 *GATAD2A*, and multiple oncogenes among nuclear factors and genes products that are likely to function in
15 transformation of HR-, HER2- breast cancer, or triple negative breast cancer.
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Results

We measured total transcription in the normal breast and in primary tumors from humans with triple negative breast cancer to discover nuclear factors mobilized and contributing to generation and maintenance of the transformed state in triple negative breast cancer. We also measured whole transcription in isolated single cells obtained from bulk primary tumors of women with triple negative breast cancer to validate our findings and rule out contributions of the stroma to nuclear factor expression.

Figure 1: Chromatin associated factors are activated in triple negative breast cancer.

1A: Primary tumors from humans with TNBC.

GSE185645

n=1 normal tissue of the breast (control)

n=33 primary tumor of the breast; TNBC; human

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
8152668	2.94E-03	-3.4942791	-1.5667	-1.59845625	ATAD2	177/	
8024078	1.30E-01	-1.5931238	-4.563	-0.27046149	ARID3A	3915/33252	

1B: Single tumor cells isolated from the primary tumors of humans with TNBC.

GSE38959

n=13 normal mammary ductal epithelial cells of the breast (control)

n=30 laser-capture isolated single tumor cells; primary tumor (TNBC)

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
35827	2.33E-09	-7.4274874	11.29459	-2.6507701	ATAD2	939/	
19460	1.90E-02	-2.4334557	-3.956429	-0.881806	ARID3A	11183/45015	

Figure 2: A series of oncogenes mobilized in triple negative breast cancer.

2A: Primary tumors from humans with TNBC.

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
8119161	1.64E-01	-1.4588859	-4.7274	-0.6278321	PIM1	4922/	
8175039	9.44E-02	-1.7762445	-4.3229	-0.94701852	ELF4	2857/	
7961865	8.32E-02	-1.8462371	-4.2267	-0.74845614	KRAS	2527/	
8172345	7.75E-02	-1.8842964	-4.1735	-0.33043547	ELK1	2342/	

2B: Single tumor cells isolated from the primary tumors of humans with TNBC.

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
21725	9.21E-08	-6.3526873	7.706281	-2.1917494	PIM1	932/	
23816	1.82E-07	-6.1544632	7.043764	-2.563696	ELF4	1061/	
11392	5.87E-05	-4.4334869	1.447422	-1.068542	KRAS	3288/	
5875	6.38E-03	-2.8608398	-2.971268	-0.7727844	ELK1	9090/	

Figure 3: Homeobox transcription factors are transcriptionally induced in TNBC.

3A: Primary tumors from humans with TNBC.

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
8032290	3.00E-01	-1.0713557	-5.1385	-0.27518573	TCF3	9438/	
8118086	2.48E-01	-1.1989556	-5.0144	-0.43026428	TCF19	7697/	
7979281	6.63E-02	-1.9685586	-4.0534	-1.01036403	WDHD1	2030/	
8103728	2.70E-02	-2.4311735	-3.3478	-1.24141452	HMGB2	935/	
8170468	3.44E-02	-2.3096046	-3.5397	-1.0650712	HMGB3	1122/	
8016468	1.30E-01	-1.5945911	-4.5611	-0.32623567	HOXB7	3900/	

3B: Single tumor cells isolated from the primary tumors of humans with TNBC.

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
29635	4.75E-06	-5.1955132	3.873602	-1.305221	TCF3	2017/	
17916	4.61E-07	-5.8827846	6.138187	-2.142519	TCF19	1257/	
22608	4.72E-06	-5.1970837	3.878713	-1.9069591	WDHD1	2016/	
30883	9.24E-07	-5.6787235	5.460972	-1.5931686	HMGB2	1449/	
41530	2.51E-12	-9.4908361	17.955902	-3.0842107	HMGB3	129/	
15293	1.16E-05	-4.9268266	3.004965	-2.0471648	HOXB7	2415/	

Figure 4: Expression of a thyroid hormone-associated factor described to function in DNA repair, *TRIP13*, in TNBC.

4A: Primary tumors from humans with TNBC.

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
8104234	1.55E-01	-1.491655	-4.6883	-1.3748492	TRIP13	4638/	

4B: Single tumor cells isolated from the primary tumors of humans with TNBC.

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
5082	2.08E-09	-7.4601107	11.402835	-2.2532915	TRIP13	428/	

Figure 5: TNBC is depleted for a nuclear co-factor, *NRIP2*.

5A: Primary tumors from humans with TNBC.

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
7960331	1.71E-02	2.6561496	-2.9831	0.65490635	NRIP2	660/	

5B: Single tumor cells isolated from the primary tumors of humans with TNBC.

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
18932	5.03E-05	4.4811865	1.595501	0.6393187	NRIP2	3192/	

1 **Figure 6: TNBC is enriched for a nuclear co-factor, *GATAD2A*.**

2 6A: Primary tumors from humans with TNBC.

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ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
8027169	1.05E-01	-1.7172872	-4.402	-0.51128233	GATAD2A	3134/	

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5 6B: Single tumor cells isolated from the primary tumors of humans with TNBC.

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ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
7083	3.39E-07	-5.9725983	6.437144	-0.9676608	GATAD2A	1196/	

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8 **Figure 7: *NRIP2* interacts with *ZNF540*, a transcriptional repressor.**

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Node1	Node2	N1 string id	N2 string id	experimentally determined interaction	score
NRIP2	ZNF540	9606.ENSP00000337501	9606.ENSP00000324598	0.042	0.418

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11 **Figure 8: *ZNF540* expression is depleted in basal subtype breast cancer, the PAM50 subtype whose hormone receptor expression overlaps with the triple negative histological subtype.**

12 GSE87049

13 n=35 normal breast

14 n=14 primary tumors of the breast; basal subtype

15 **Discussion**

16 We described here the discovery of nuclear factors important for the induction and maintenance of transformation in triple negative breast cancer. These factors included the chromatin-associated molecule *ATAD2* and the GATA family molecule *GATAD2A*. We discovered *NRIP2* as a nuclear factor whose expression was depleted in TNBC, which shares significant transcriptional overlap with the PAM50 molecular subtype basal-like or basal subtype breast cancer. We identified a protein-protein interaction between *NRIP2* and *ZNF540*, a transcriptional repressor, and found that *ZNF540* expression was similarly depleted in the basal subtype (Figure 8) and in triple negative breast cancer (data not shown).

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We identified nuclear factors contributing to transformation in triple negative breast cancer by measuring total transcription in bulk tumors and single tumor cells from humans with triple negative breast cancer using published microarray and RNA-sequencing data (GSE185645 and GSE38959) in conjunction with R (computation)-based quantitative methods. We used STRING for protein-protein interaction studies.